

Review Article

MALDI-TOF MS: A Microbiological Perspective

¹Dixit K. Parasana, ²I. H. Kalyani, ³P. M. Makwana

¹Ph. D. Scholar, ²Professor and Head, ³Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Microbiology, College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry, Navsari

Introduction

Mass spectrometry is an analytical technique in which chemical compounds are ionized into charged molecules and ratio of their mass to charge (m/z) is measured (Everley *et al.*, 2008). Matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI) is an ionization technique that uses a laser energy absorbing matrix to create ions from large molecules with minimal fragmentation (Hillenkamp *et al.*, 1991).

The basic principle of TOF is that ions of different m/z are dispersed in time during their flight along a field-free drift path of known length. All the ions start their journey at the same time or at least within a sufficiently short time interval, the lighter ones will arrive earlier at the detector than the heavier ones (Yates, 1998).

Matrix and laser are main components in MALDI. Matrix is of a fairly low molecular weight but are large enough not to evaporate during sample preparation or while standing in the mass spectrometer. They are often acidic, therefore act as a proton source to encourage ionization of the analyte. Cinnamic acid derivatives ferulic acid, caffeic acid and sinapinic acid commonly used as the matrix. α -Cyano-4-hydroxy cinnamic acid (CHCA) is suitable for the detection of peptides (Beavis and Chait, 1989., Strupat *et al.*, 1991., Beavis *et al.*, 1992).

MALDI techniques typically employ the use of UV lasers such as: Nitrogen lasers (337 nm), Frequency-tripled Nd:YAG lasers (355 nm) and Frequency quadrupled Nd:YAG lasers (266 nm) (Dreisewerd, 2014).

History

The concept of using mass spectrometry for identification of bacteria was proposed in 1975 by Anhalt and Fenselau. In 1985, Koichi Tanaka described a “soft desorption ionization” method using ultra-fine metal powder and glycerol that enabled mass spectrometric analysis of biological macro molecules, for which he was awarded the Nobel Prize in Chemistry. The term matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI) was coined in 1985 by Franz Hillenkamp, Michael Karas and their colleagues. The first MALDI-TOF MS system capable of microbial identification, termed “MALDI Biotyper” was developed by Bruker Daltonics in 2009.

Principle of MALDI-TOF MS

The sample for analysis by MALDI MS is prepared by mixing or coating with solution of an energy-absorbent, organic compound called matrix. When the matrix crystallizes on drying, the sample entrapped within the matrix also co-crystallizes. The sample within the matrix is ionized in an automated mode with a laser beam. Desorption and ionization with the laser beam generate singly protonated ions from analytes in the sample. The protonated ions are then accelerated at a fixed potential, where these separate from each other on the basis of their mass-to-charge ratio (m/z). The charged analytes are then detected and measured using TOF analyser (Singhal *et al.*, 2015). During MALDI-TOF analysis, the m/z ratio of anion is measured by determining the time required for it to travel the length of the flight tube. Based on the TOF information, a characteristic spectrum called Peptide Mass Fingerprint (PMF) is generated for analytes in the sample. Identification of microbes by MALDI-TOF MS is done by comparing the PMF of unknown organism with the PMFs contained in the database (Karas and Kruger, 2003).

Applications In Bacteriology

MALDI-TOF technology allows accurate bacterial identification of a large variety of species in reduced time, from between 24 and 48 hours to a few minutes, with a small amount of microbial biomass required for the analysis (10^4 to 10^6 CFU). Colonies are picked from agar medium with a sterile tip and smeared in a thin film onto MALDI target plate, overlaid with matrix and introduced in the mass spectrometer for data acquisition (De Carolis *et al.*, 2014).

Detection Of Antibiotic Degradation

This approach primarily determines the beta-lactam antibiotic resistance. Resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics is mainly due to beta-lactamase expression, which hydrolyses the beta-lactam ring and inactivates the antibiotic activity. The hydrolysis of a beta-lactam ring by beta-lactamase corresponds to the addition of a Water molecular, and this reaction leads to an 18 Da mass change, which can be easily detected by MALDI-TOF MS (Sakarikou *et al.*, 2017).

Phenotypic Antibiotic Resistance Analysis

This method is similar to the phenotypic observation of antibiotic resistance in microorganisms. The advantage of this method is that it is faster than conventional technology, as it only requires 2–3-hour incubation. In principle, it can be used to detect any mechanism of antibiotic resistance by optimizing the growth of microorganisms in the presence of antibiotics (Van belkum *et al.*, 2017). When micro-organisms are incubated with antibiotics, they are grown in medium containing isotopically labelled amino acids. Only resistant, growing microorganisms are able to incorporate the labelled amino acids. By comparing the resistant profile spectra with the standard spectra, the AST

results can be determined in hours (Jung *et al.*, 2016).

Application In Mycology

As yeasts possess a thick cell wall, its disruption requires an additional extraction step compared to bacterial protocol. Colonies are picked and inoculated in 70% ethanol, the suspension is pelleted, dried, and resuspended in 70% formic acid and acetonitrile. After a centrifugation step, one microliter of supernatant is applied on the MALDI target plate and dried, covered with matrix, and analysed (De carolis *et al.*, 2014).

Application In Virology

The use of MALDI-TOF MS in virology has advanced less as it has in bacteriology or mycology. This might be a consequence of the relatively low protein content of viruses, higher molecular weight of viral proteins (>20,000 Da) and a probable carry-over of debris of the cell substrate in which viruses are cultured *in vitro* (Kliem and Sauer, 2012).

Benefits of MALDI-TOF

The improved performance of MALDI-TOF MS over traditional methods seems to have contributed to an increase in the reporting of some relatively rare species. Bacteria with complex nutritional requirements are particularly difficult to identify to the species level using traditional methods, but readily identified by MALDI-TOF MS (Rychert *et al.*, 2015).

Limitations of MALDI-TOF

MALDI-TOF unable to identify some organisms due to lack of sufficient spectra in the database. The MALDI-TOF MS technology failed to distinguish *E. coli* and *Shigella* spp. or discriminate among species of the mitis complex of Streptococci (Hou *et al.*, 2019).

Conclusions

MALDI-TOF MS relies on the detection of mass to charge ratio abbreviated as m/z of ribosomal proteins of the bacteria, which helps to provide a unique mass spectrum of the bacteria within a short period of time. This technique works on the ionization principle and laser is used as a source of ionisation energy. α -cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid is a most Commonly used matrix in MALDI-TOF. The identification is provided by comparing the spectrum with the spectra of reference strains based on the closest match. The technique can be used in clinical microbiology to identify bacteria, yeast and mould up to genus and species level and useful for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. MALDI-TOF can be used in detection of parasites and diagnosis of cancer.

Future Prospects

Further prospective studies are warranted to increase MALDI-TOF MS reliability to directly identify pathogens in biological fluids, such as urine samples and blood cultures. The provision for

integrating in-built databases in the public databases of MALDI-TOF MS, as well as development of inexpensive and user-friendly softwares for comparisons and analyses would further increase the credibility of MALDI-TOF MS in future.

References

- Anhalt, J. and Fenselau, C. (1975). Identification of bacteria using mass spectrometry. *Analytical Chemistry*. **47**: 219–25.
- Beavis, R. C. and Chait, B. T. (1989). Matrix-assisted laser-desorption mass spectrometry using 355 nm radiation. *Rapid Communication in Mass Spectrometry*. **3**: 436–439.
- Beavis, R. C., Chaudhary, T. and Chait, B. T. (1992). α -Cyano-4-hydroxy cinnamic acid as a matrix for matrix-assisted laser desorption mass spectrometry. *Organic Mass Spectrometry*. **27**:156–158.
- De Carolis, E., Vella, A., Vaccaro, L., Torelli, R., Spanu, T., Fiori, B., Posteraro, B. and Sanguinetti, M. (2014). Application of MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry in clinical diagnostic microbiology. *The Journal of Infection in Developing Countries*. **8**(09): 1081-1088.
- Dreisewerd, K. (2014). "Recent methodological advances in MALDI mass spectrometry". *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*. **406** (9–10): 2261–2278.
- Everley, R. A., Mott, T. M., Wyatt, S. A., Toney, D. M., and Croley, T. R. (2008). Liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry characterization of Escherichia coli and Shigella species. *Journal of American Society for Mass Spectrometry*. **19**: 1621–1628
- Hillenkamp, F., Karas, M., Beavis, R. C., Chait, B. T. (1991). "Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry of biopolymers". *Analytical Chemistry*. **63** (24): 1193A–1203A.
- Hou, T.Y., Chiang-Ni, C. and Teng, S. H. (2019). Current status of MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry in clinical microbiology. *Journal of food and drug analysis*. **27**(2): 404-414.
- Jung, J. S., Hamacher, C., Gross, B., Sparbier, K., Lange, C., Kostrzewa, M. and Schubert, S. (2016). Evaluation of a semiquantitative matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization–time of flight mass spectrometry method for rapid antimicrobial susceptibility testing of positive blood cultures. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*. **54**(11): 2820-2824.
- Karas, M., Kruger, R. (2003). "Ion Formation in MALDI: The Cluster Ionization Mechanism". *Chemical Reviews*. **103**(2): 427–440.
- Kliem, M., and Sauer, S. (2012). The essence on mass spectrometry based microbial diagnostics. *Current opinion in microbiology*. **15**(3): 397-402.
- Rychert, J. (2019). Benefits and limitations of MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry for the identification of microorganisms. *Journal of Infection*. **2**(4).
- Sakarikou, C., Ciotti, M., Dolfa, C., Angeletti, S. and Favalli, C. (2017). Rapid detection of carbapenemase-producing Klebsiella pneumoniae strains derived from blood cultures by Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization-Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS). *BMC microbiology*. **17**(1): 1-8.
- Singhal, N., Kumar, M., Kanaujia, P.K. and Viridi, J.S. (2015). MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry: an emerging technology for microbial identification and diagnosis. *Frontiers in microbiology*. **6**: 791.
- Strupat, K., Karas, M. and Hillenkamp, F. (1991). 2, 5-Dihydroxy benzoic acid: a new matrix for laser desorption–ionization mass spectrometry. *International Journal of Mass Spectrometry and Ion Processes*. **111**: 89–102.
- Van Belkum, A., Welker, M., Pincus, D., Charrier, J. P. and Girard, V. (2017). Matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry in clinical microbiology: what are the current issues?. *Annals of laboratory medicine*. **37**(6): 475.
- Yates III, J. R. (1998). Mass spectrometry and the age of the proteome. *Journal of Mass Spectrometry*. **33**(1): 1-19.